

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

The temporal response to inhibition of ERBB2 (HER2).

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We measured total transcription following inhibition of HER2 in human breast cancer cells with a small molecule inhibitor or monoclonal antibody targeting the epidermal growth factor family receptor. Based on these analyses and two further systems biologic analyses that measured the compensatory response in breast cancer cells engineered to develop resistance to trastuzumab in vitro and in the tumors of humans that failed to achieve a pathologic complete response following treatment with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer to identify candidate genes that function in treatment resistant behavior in HER2+ breast cancer we describe here a set of genes identified without bias whose combined pharmacologic inhibition targets compensatory signaling following a primary clinical intervention targeting growth factor signaling in cancer and predicted to provide some level of efficacy in restoring treatment response in treatment resistant HER2+ breast cancer.

Results

The basic set of components required for cell cycle progression and execution of necessary metabolic functions include growth factors, the biochemicals that comprise the molecules contained within the cell, and the basic commodity required for active energetic transactions in a cell, ATP. A systematic approach to restriction of growth factor-induced proliferation thus considers the growth factor composition of the tumor, the ability of the growth factor to transduce a signal, the ability of the tumor to sustain catalysis of biosynthetic reactions based on quantity of biomolecule present, the ATP synthesis potential of the tumor that defines the amount of ATP available to sustain viable tumor function, and maintenance of energy homeostasis in the cell, performed by multiple pathways that form a nutrient sensing center which utilizes energetic and nutritional inputs to balance the transfer of energy in the cell.

Growth factors provide mitogenic support of signal transduction: proliferative function (cell division). The soluble factor is able to convert the growth promoting potential of the ligand to a transcriptional response characterized by the expression and/or silencing of genes whose products effect ligand-dependent growth control (i.e., mitogenic or proliferative response). Thus, the growth factor possesses an intrinsic growth promoting value that is proportional to the quantity of factor available and quantity of cognate receptor.

The second major limiting factor for sustained proliferation following growth factor signaling is the quantity of ATP present.

The most conventionally understood form of energy utilized by the cell is ATP: reactions that are active processes ("work") that require energy to drive the pathway utilize the chemical energy stored in the phosphate bond of ATP; the traction is coupled to ATP hydrolysis. An understanding of cellular energy requiring cognizance of complex cellular environments that are functionally viable, where the cell or tissue survives and thrives despite limited nutritional and energetic input.

The third major consideration in an energetically constrained environment is the machinery of the mitochondria that together function in ATP synthesis. Electrical function of the mitochondria related to induction of cell death, while not an ATP synthetic function of the mitochondria, integrates signals derived from cell death pathways and sensing of changes in energy homeostasis and nutrient state that, as a result of the ability to modulated survival decisions following altered electrical activity, is associated with effective growth factor induced proliferation, and thus a second component of the third consideration in a systems based target discovery for growth control through regulation of nutrient sensing and energy homeostasis.

A finite quantity of the basic components that are required for the synthesis of the molecules and structures that comprise the cell thus limits unrestricted cell cycle in a growth factor activated environment: nucleic acids, amino acids, fatty acids and carbohydrates. Replication of the daughter strand (genome duplication), the process that imposed a requirement for nucleic acid synthesis, resulting from the specific importance of DNTP synthesis in cancer cell proliferation, can be considered separate in an energetic-centered systems discovery approach to growth factor activation in a cancer. Similarly, because metabolism of lipids, albeit important in transformed states, is less proximally-related to energy and nutrient sensing associated with growth factor signaling and the cycling it permits then global proteomic output or metabolism of energy stored as glycogen based on the intrinsic link of ATP synthesis and the glycolytic pathway.

1 Thus, a third major consideration in a systems biologic approach for nutrient and energy restriction in
2 cancer, in addition to the growth factor system and ATP is the protein synthesis machinery (i.e., ribosome)
3 that sustains a level of translational efficiency required by rate of cycling and enzymes that influence
4 energy and nutrient availability in the cell by permitting enhanced anabolic and catabolic activity for
5 carbohydrate recycling (e.g., phosphofructokinase). Regulation of carbohydrate metabolism is amenable to
6 changes in glycolytic flux to meet energetic requirements of the tumor during growth factor-induced cell
7 cycle activation.

8 Finally, a fourth major consideration in a systems level energy restriction strategy based on inhibition of
9 cellular targets that enable successful energetic restriction in cancer (including cancer subtypes that are
10 defined by expression of a growth factor receptor) by discovery based design of a chemotherapeutic
11 regimen is the systems that regulate the transfer of energy in a cell during normal homeostatic function.
12 This collection of pathways is defined by nutrient and energy sensing functions which together control
13 transfer of energy in the cell by regulation of metabolic and proliferative function. These pathways include
14 components of the mTOR, PI3-kinase and AKT pathways. Secretory pathway machinery with known or
15 suggested functions in nutrient uptake, transport, or recycling (genes encoded by the Rab, Vps, Sec,
16 CCDC, and Stx families) transporters that facilitate nutrient uptake or function as regulatory components
17 of mTOR, AKT and PI3-kinase energetic signaling by receiving input from or providing feedback to the
18 nutrient sensing center are thus essential considerations for effective limitation of disease defined by
19 growth factor activation which, because nutrient sensing and transfer of energy dictated by the cancer cell
20 is essential different than found in homeostasis, will feature the induction of pathway components
21 resulting from the function of that molecule in the transfer of energy or nutrient sensing.

22 Thus, these more complex energetic environments feature adaptive regulation of a multitude of processes
23 and pathways that enable the host or the tumor cell to alter normal homeostatic limits that constrain a
24 demand for energy through regulation of metabolic pathways that feature recycling, compensatory pathway
25 responses and other anabolic and catabolic processes that are components of the human cells: nucleic
26 acids, carbohydrates, amino acids and
27
28

1 I. Identification of genes belonging to the secretory pathway or functioning in vesicular transport:

2 A. Short term HER2 inhibition in vitro.

- 3 1. Sec
4 2. Rab
5 3. Vps
6 4. CCDC

7 B. HER2+ breast cancer cells resistant to trastuzumab in vitro.

- 8 1. Sec
9 2. Rab
10 a) Rab14
11 3. Vps
12 a) Vps37C
13 4. CCDC
14 a) CCDC88C

15 C. In humans with treatment resistant HER2+ breast cancer.

- 16 1. Sec/Stx
17 a) Stx2
18 b) Stx16
19 c) Stx4
20 2. Rab
21 a) Rab22A
22 b) Rab27B
23 c) Rab14
24 3. Vps
25 a) VPS28
26 b) VPS35
27 c) VPS37C
28 4. CCDC
a) CCDC53
b) CCDC88C

II. Identification of genes that function in nutrient sensing and energy homeostasis in:

A. Short term HER2 inhibition in vitro.

1. PI3K
2. AKT
3. Ribosome
4. TBC/TSC

B. HER2+ breast cancer cells resistant to trastuzumab in vitro.

1. PI3K
2. AKT
3. Ribosome
a) RPS6KA5
b) RPS6KC1

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

- 4. TBC/TSC
 - a) TBC1D30
 - b) TBC1D5
- 5. mTOR
 - a) TSC2*

C. In humans with treatment resistant HER2+ breast cancer.

- 1. PI3K
 - a) VAC14
 - b) PIK3C2B
- 2. AKT
- 3. Ribosome
 - a) RPS6KA5
 - b) TSR3
 - c) RPS6KC1
- 4. TBC/TSC
 - a) TBC1D5
 - b) TBC1D2
 - c) TBC1D9
- 5. MTOR
 - a) TSC2

III. Identification of genes that function in kinase and phosphatase signal transduction or other growth factor related signal pathways:

A. Short term HER2 inhibition in vitro.

- 1. MAPK/CDK
- 2. Phosphatase
- 3. Growth factor pathways

B. HER2+ breast cancer cells resistant to trastuzumab in vitro.

- 1. MAPK/CDK
 - a) STK10
- 2. Phosphatase
 - a) PPP1R7
 - b) PPP3CB
- 3. Growth factor pathways
 - a) FGFR2
 - b) FGFR3

C. In humans with treatment resistant HER2+ breast cancer.

- 1. MAPK/CDK
 - a) MAPK9
 - b) STK10
 - c) MAP3K1
 - d) MAPK8

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

2. Phosphatase

- a) PPP1R7
- b) PTPN3
- c) PPP4R1
- d) PPP2R2D
- e) PTPRN
- f) PPP3CB
- g) PTPRU

3. Growth factor pathways

- a) IGF2BP2
- b) IGFBP4
- c) IGF1
- d) FGFR2
- e) FGFR3

II. Solute transporters and ABC transporters that address adaptation to nutrient restriction and multi-drug resistance.

1. Short term HER2+ inhibition *in vitro*.

- a. SLC
- b. ABC

2. *In vitro* trastuzumab resistance model at the clonal level.

- a. SLC
 - i. SLCO3A1
 - ii. SLC29A1
 - iii. SLC38A2
 - iv. SLC45A2
- b. ABC
 - i. ABCC5
 - ii. ABCB5
 - iii. ABCC13
 - iv. ABCG5
 - v. ABCA8

3. Resistance to trastuzumab *in vivo*

- a. SLC
 - i. SLC52A2
 - ii. SLCO3A1
 - iii. SLC39A6
 - iv. SLC38A2
 - v. SLC25A1
 - vi. SLC25A6
 - vii. SLC10A3
 - viii. SLC29A1
 - ix. SLC45A2
 - x. SLC25A32
 - xi. SLC25A14

- 1 b. ABC
2 i. ABCA3
3 ii. ABCC3
4 iii. ABCA8

5 4. Genes that shift homeostatic energy balance through alteration of cellular metabolism including
6 enzymes that complete cellular respiration functions in the glycolysis, oxidative reduction and electron
7 transport in the mitochondria, or other genes with carbohydrate metabolic function that enable recycling of
8 carbohydrates in the cell.

9 5. Genes that support survival of the cell or support energetic needs in ATP-sensitive environments
10 through regulation of components of the mitochondria that control induction of apoptosis through influence
11 on mitochondrial membrane potential or production of energy (ATP).

12 **Discussion**

13 We described here the discovery and design of therapeutic targeting strategy that focuses on cancer- and
14 treatment-resistance specific activation or modulation of nutrient sensing and energy homeostasis. The
15 minimal set of candidate targets includes secretory pathway components Rab14, Vps37C and CCDC88C,
16 nutrient sensing components associated with transfer of energy from or associated with the mTOR
17 pathway including RPS6KA5 and TBC1D5, and solute carriers from the SLC family of transporter genes
18 including SLCO3A1, SLC29A1, SLC38A2 and SLC45A2. The complete regimen includes targets for which
19 inhibitors already exist or for which inhibitors exist but are only for use in research or development: this
20 included the growth factor receptors FGFR2 and FGFR3, the kinase STK10, and phosphatases PPP1R7
21 and PPP3CB.

22 FGFR2/3 inhibitors approved for use in the clinic include erdafitinib. PPP3CB is related to calcineurin and
23 one study described inhibition of PPP3CB by calcineurin inhibitor by cyclosporin A and FK506. An inhibitor
24 of STK10 has been described.

25 Limitations of secretory pathway targeting described here included the lack of available pharmacologic
26 tools to target the molecules but for which any known or intrinsically limiting factor that prevents
27 development of a nutrient restriction centered strategy through development of epitope specific
28 immunoglobulin-based inhibitors is not thought to exist.

Co-administration of an ABCA8 inhibitor was indicated by study of treatment resistance and compensatory
signaling in HER2+ breast cancer following treatment with trastuzumab. Since the targets were selected
based on compensatory signaling and changes induced associated with resistant disease or resistance in
vitro, the therapeutic index of the selected targets in treatment-naive, non-resistant patients is not
understood. Factors that support study of usage of such an approach exist and include an elevated rate of
CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer. Similarly, because the regimen has not yet been
studied in or approved for use in humans, efficacy of the targeting approach, delivered in conjunction with
standard trastuzumab or with trastuzumab and neoadjuvant chemotherapy, and in naive patients
compared to the treatment-resistant or relapsed population is not yet understood.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We performed systems biologic discovery of candidate genes for therapeutic targeting in treatment resistant breast cancer by measuring total transcription using R-based computational methods and microarray or RNA-sequencing of cells that model resistance to HER,2+ inhibition that are engineered to develop resistance to trastuzumab in vitro at the clonal level (GSE15043) and primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer with pCR or residual disease (RD) (GSE20194). An asterisk indicates the gene was not significantly differentially expressed in that experimental system but that the gene fulfilled transcriptome differential expression in a separate system and thus considered a viable candidate gene in the discovery approach or otherwise an important event to describe in development of the targeting strategy.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Reference

Shakhova I, Li Y, Yu F, Kaneko Y, Nakamura Y, Ohira M, Izumi H, Mae T, Varfolomeeva SR, Rummyantsev AG, Nakagawara A. PPP3CB contributes to poor prognosis through activating nuclear factor of activated T-cells signaling in neuroblastoma. *Mol Carcinog.* 2019 Mar;58(3):426-435. doi: 10.1002/mc.22939. Epub 2018 Dec 13. PMID: 30457174.

Serafim RAM, Sorrell FJ, Berger BT, Collins RJ, Vasconcelos SNS, Massirer KB, Knapp S, Bennett J, Fedorov O, Patel H, Zuercher WJ, Elkins JM. Discovery of a Potent Dual SLK/STK10 Inhibitor Based on a Maleimide Scaffold. *J Med Chem.* 2021 Sep 23;64(18):13259-13278. doi: 10.1021/acs.jmedchem.0c01579. Epub 2021 Aug 31. PMID: 34463505.